

Complexes of Thiovanol with Oxomolybdenum(V), Ruthenium(II) and Iridium(III)

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In continuation of our work¹, the present communication describes the preparation and characterisation of the complexes of thiovanol (CH₂-SHCHOHCH₂-OH) with oxomolybdenum(V), ruthenium(II) and iridium(III).

Results and Discussion

The subnormal magnetic moment value of the oxomolybdenum(V) complex (1.46 B.M.) may be attributed to spin-orbit coupling and metal-metal interaction². The Ru^{II} and Ir^{III} complexes are diamagnetic in nature.

Electronic spectrum of the Mo^V complex gives two bands at 14 600 and 23 100 cm⁻¹ which may be assigned³ to $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{xz}$, $d_{yz} \rightarrow d_{xy}$ and $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$ transitions respectively. The Ru^{II} complex exhibits two bands at 21 000 and 28 500 cm⁻¹ corresponding to transitions⁴ ${}^1T_{1g} \leftarrow {}^1A_{1g}$ and ${}^1T_{2g} \leftarrow {}^1A_{1g}$ respectively. The Ir^{III} complex shows only one band at 32 000 cm⁻¹ which may be assigned⁵ to ${}^1T_{1g} \leftarrow {}^1A_{1g}$ transition. The electronic spectra of the complexes suggest octahedral geometry.

A comparison of the ir spectra of the ligand and the complexes shows the disappearance of the ligand S—H stretching frequency (appearing at 2 560 cm⁻¹) in the spectra of the complexes. This indicates involvement of sulphur of the sulphhydryl group in coordination. This is further confirmed by lowering of the C—S stretching frequency from 660 cm⁻¹ in the ligand to 650—645 cm⁻¹ in the complexes. Lowering of primary alcoholic C—O stretching frequency appearing at 1 040 cm⁻¹ in the spectrum of the ligand to 1 030—1 025 cm⁻¹ in the spectra of the complexes, reveals that primary alcoholic group is involved in the coordination. The oxomolybdenum(V) complex displays a broad and very strong band at 950 cm⁻¹. The

$\nu(\text{Mo} \begin{array}{c} \diagup \text{O} \diagdown \\ \text{---} \end{array} \text{Mo})$ band has been found at 800—840 cm⁻¹ supporting⁶ the oxobridging in the complex.

In far-infrared region, the ligand and its Mo complex display a number of bands at 600—300 cm⁻¹. The band at 330 cm⁻¹ has been tentatively assigned to $\nu_{\text{Mo}-\text{Cl}}$ in the oxomolybdenum complex⁷.

Experimental

The ligand was obtained as a gift sample from Evans Chemetics³. All other chemicals were of A.R. grade.

Dichlorotetrakis-thiovanolato-μ-oxodimolybdenum(V) chloride. [Mo₂O(C₃H₇O₂S)₄Cl₂]Cl₂: An aqueous solution of ammonium molybdate (0.1M; 40 ml) was made alkaline with ammonium hydroxide solution. It was then treated with 5N HCl and to it was added 0.1M thiovanol solution (200 ml) at pH 4.5 when the colour intensified. The solution was concentrated on a water-bath and the resulting green solid was washed with alcohol, acetone and petroleum ether and dried at 80°. It was found insoluble in water and common organic solvents.

Chlorothiovanolatotriaquoruthenium(II). [Ru(C₃H₇O₂S)Cl(H₂O)₃]: A mixture of 0.1M thiovanol solution (200 ml) and 0.1M ruthenium(III) chloride was concentrated on a water-bath. To it ethanol was added and a pink coloured solid was separated at pH 4.5. It was then washed with water, alcohol and acetone and dried at 80°. The complex was found to be insoluble in water and common organic solvents, and was hygroscopic in nature.

Tris-thiovanolatoiridium(III). [Ir(C₃H₇O₂S)₃]: Thiovanol (0.1M) was added to iridium trichloride solution (0.1M; 40 ml) and pH of the solution was adjusted to 4.0. The mixture was concentrated on a water-bath. The resulting yellow solid was washed with water, alcohol, acetone and petroleum ether and dried at 85°. It was found insoluble in water, alcohol and common organic solvents.

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF THE COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	Analysis %: Found/Calcd.		
		M	S	Cl
[Mo ₂ O(C ₃ H ₇ O ₂ S) ₄ Cl ₂]Cl ₂	Green	24.40 (24.67)	16.10 16.45	17.60 18.10
[Ru(C ₃ H ₇ O ₂ S)Cl(H ₂ O) ₃]	Pink	33.76 (33.97)	10.60 10.75	11.85 11.93
[Ir(C ₃ H ₇ O ₂ S) ₃]	Yellow	37.29 (37.45)	18.50 18.76	—

TABLE 2—SPECTRAL BANDS (cm⁻¹) OF THE COMPOUNDS

Oxo-MoV complex	RuII complex	IrIII complex	Thiovanol	Assignment
—	—	—	2 560	ν_{SH}
1 400	1 405	1 425	1 425	δ_{OH}
1 080	1 080	1 080	1 080	$\nu_{\text{C-O}}(\text{S})$
1 025	1 030	1 025	1 040	$\nu_{\text{C-O}}(\text{P})$
950	—	—	—	—
830	—	—	—	—
645	650	645	660	$\nu_{\text{C-S}}$